

ADVERTISING AND PR-TECHNOLOGIES INFLUENCE ON CREATION AND PROMOTION RUSSIAN AND SPANISH REGIONS IMAGE AS TOURIST DESTINATIONS

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Abstract

The article considers the current, previously unaffected in scientific research, problem of the influence of advertising and PR technologies on the creation and promotion of the image of Russian and Spanish regions as tourist destinations. A strategy is being developed and proposed to increase the rating of tourist destinations of Spanish and Russian resorts based on the introduction of advertising and PR technologies. The author notes that at present there is an increasing need for effective advertising of tourist organizations, which need to regulate the impact on the state of public opinion of target audiences. For this reason, the increasing importance of the information and communication component of the activities of tourist destinations is being updated. The high importance of the image of tourist destination for the successful promotion of the region stimulates the study of this topic, the research of existing experience. As a result, the author studies the practice of applying advertising and PR technologies in the formation of the region's image, determines its effectiveness. It is further concluded that, in the modern information age, the quantity and quality of information in the World Wide Web largely depends on the development of tourism in specific regions and countries. It is also emphasized that it is necessary to monitor the development of events in order to respond in time to changing situations.

Keywords: Advertising; PR-Technologies; Image Promotion; Tourist and Recreational Space; Tourist Deprivation.

A PUBLICIDADE E AS PR-TECNOLOGIAS INFLUENCIAM A CRIAÇÃO E PROMOÇÃO DA IMAGEM DAS REGIÕES RUSSAS E ESPANHOLAS COMO DESTINOS TURÍSTICOS

Resumo

O artigo considera o problema atual, anteriormente não afetado na investigação científica, da influência da publicidade e das tecnologias de relações públicas na criação e promoção da imagem das regiões russas e espanholas como destinos turísticos. Desenvolve-se e propõe-se uma estratégia para aumentar a classificação dos destinos turísticos das estâncias turísticas espanholas e russas com base na introdução de publicidade e tecnologias de relações públicas. Observa-se que atualmente existe uma necessidade crescente de publicidade eficaz das organizações turísticas, que precisam de regular o impacto sobre o estado da opinião pública dos públicos-alvo. Por este motivo, a crescente importância do componente de informação e comunicação das atividades dos destinos turísticos está sendo atualizada. A elevada importância da imagem do destino turístico para o sucesso da promoção da região estimula o estudo deste tema, a investigação da experiência existente. Como resultado, verifica-se a prática da aplicação da publicidade e das tecnologias de relações públicas na formação da imagem da região, determina a sua eficácia. Conclui-se ainda que, na era moderna da informação, a quantidade e a qualidade da informação na World Wide Web dependem em grande medida do desenvolvimento do turismo em regiões e países específicos. Adicionalmente, é necessário monitorizar o desenvolvimento dos acontecimentos para responder a tempo à situações em mudança.

Palavras-chave: Publicidade; Tecnologias de Relações Públicas; Promoção da Imagem; Espaço Turístico e Recreativo; Privação Turística.

INFLUENCIA DE LA PUBLICIDAD Y LAS TECNOLOGÍAS DE RELACIONES PÚBLICAS EN LA CREACIÓN Y PROMOCIÓN DE LA IMAGEN DE LAS REGIONES RUSAS Y ESPAÑOLAS COMO DESTINOS TURÍSTICOS

Resumen

El artículo considera el problema actual, hasta ahora no tratado en la investigación científica, de la influencia de las tecnologías publicitarias y de relaciones públicas en la creación y promoción de la imagen de las regiones rusas y españolas como destinos turísticos. Se desarrolla y propone una estrategia para aumentar la valoración de los destinos turísticos de España y Rusia basada en la introducción de tecnologías publicitarias y de relaciones públicas. En la actualidad existe una creciente necesidad de publicidad efectiva de las organizaciones turísticas, que necesitan regular el impacto en el estado de la opinión pública del público objetivo. Por esta razón, se está actualizando la creciente importancia del componente de información y comunicación de las actividades de los destinos turísticos. La gran importancia de la imagen del destino turístico para el éxito de la promoción de la región estimula el estudio de este tema, la investigación de la experiencia existente. Como resultado, se verifica que la práctica de la aplicación de las tecnologías de publicidad y relaciones públicas en la formación de la imagen de la región determina su eficacia. Además, se concluye que, en la era moderna de la información, la cantidad y la calidad de la información en la World Wide Web depende en gran medida del desarrollo del turismo en regiones y países específicos. También se subraya que es necesario seguir la evolución de los acontecimientos para responder a tiempo a las situaciones cambiantes.

Palabras clave: Publicidad; Tecnologías de Relaciones Públicas; Promoción de la Imagen; Espacio Turístico y Recreativo; Privación del Turismo.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Today, tourism is one of the largest, most profitable and most dynamic sectors of the world economy. The successful development of tourism has an impact on such key sectors of the economy as transport and communications, trade, construction, agriculture, production of consumer goods, etc. Thus, the creation of a developed tourism industry is of great importance as one of the effective directions of the structural restructuring of the economy of Russia and other countries.

In modern conditions, the competition for sales markets, investments, labor and much more is getting tougher every year. According to Jensen (2002), the use of such a tool as marketing is a prerequisite for the activities of all entities that aim to sell a product or service and strengthen their competitive position. Tourist services also require the use of a marketing approach, or rather the marketing of a territory or places.

Kotler et al. (1993) believed that progressive modern information and communication technologies provide new opportunities: with the help of means and methods of advertising and PR technologies, it exercises a regulatory effect on the state of economic, political, and cultural development of society.

Volkova, et al. (2018), as well as Castels and Himanen (2002) argued that it is the information activity of subjects in the tourism industry that leads to an increase in the communicative impact in order to form the preferences of the target audience, broadcast cultural knowledge, norms, traditions and values, transform old into new stereotypes and behavioral practices.

The issues of regional and territorial image, the problems of the formation tourist's destination, in the last few years have become the subject of attention of the Russian Federation government, heads of regional and municipal authorities, Russian and foreign scientists, specialists, practitioners of the tourism industry, brand developers.

This is evidenced by documents approved by the government, urban development programs, materials of scientific and practical conferences, publications in print and electronic media devoted to topical issues of promoting the territory and improving its economic and socio-cultural status.

The relevance of the topic "regional image" is also connected with the high potential of attracting additional financial sources, increasing the tourist flow, expanding the choice of tourist services in the region.

Afanasyev (2016), paying special attention to the region's image problem, reflects the current state of economic policy, population, social institutions,

geography, climate, as well as features of history, culture, science and education, religion, mentality, in general, the level of development and progress of the territory.

Hvass and Munar (2008), referring to the research of the influence of advertising and PR technologies on the creation and promotion of tourist's image destinations, argued that at the moment there is an increasing need for effective advertising of tourist organizations that need to regulate the impact on the state of public opinion of target audiences.

For this reason, the increasing importance of the information and communication component of the activities of tourist destinations has been actualized in modern society. Schmitt (2001) argued in his writings that the high importance of the image of a tourist destination for the successful promotion of the region stimulates extensive research on this topic, the research of existing experience.

At the same time, despite the large number of works on this topic, it remains important to study the practice of using advertising and PR technologies in shaping the image of the region, determining their effectiveness.

Thus, this article examines the actual problem of the influence of advertising and PR technologies on the creation and promotion of the image of Russian and Spanish regions as tourist destinations, which has not been previously touched upon in scientific research. In particular, we will consider such a Russian region as the Caucasian Mineral Waters and the Spanish region – the autonomous region of Andalusia.

The purpose of the research is to identify the effectiveness of the influence of advertising and PR technologies on the creation and promotion of the region's image as a tourist destination (using the example of Spanish and domestic resorts); to develop a strategy to increase the rating of tourist destinations of Spanish and domestic resorts based on the introduction of advertising and PR technologies.

2 THEORETICAL REVIEW

Caucasian Mineral Waters is the largest specially protected ecological and resort region of Russia of federal significance, originated about 200 years ago, which has no analogues on the Eurasian continent in terms of richness, diversity, quantity and value of mineral waters and therapeutic mud.

This is the most picturesque corner of the North Caucasus, which has always attracted vacationers and tourists. Resorts of Caucasian Mineral Waters, such as Kislovodsk, Essentuki, Zheleznovodsk, Pyatigorsk, are located at an altitude of 600-1000 m above sea level,

this is due to one of their main therapeutic factors - the purest mountain air.

The main wealth and the main therapeutic means in the resorts of Kavminvod are mineral springs. More than 300 healing mineral springs are concentrated in this unique corner, surrounded by a picturesque ring of the Caucasus Mountains. They have long attracted the attention of vacationers. In the treatment of Kavminvody, a combination of basic balneological resources (mineral waters, mud) and a healing climate is used.

As emphasized by A.P. Gorbunov, A.P. Kolyadin, L.A. Burnasheva, L.Kh. Gazgireeva, O.Y. Kosenko (2018). There are many wonderful places in the vicinity of the Caucasian Mineral Waters that attract attention with the beauty of nature, climate, historical and natural monuments.

The main wealth of Caucasian Mineral Waters is unique in diversity, healing properties of mineral springs, supplemented by deposits of therapeutic mud. Lake Tambukan has an important balneological significance in the region of Caucasian Mineral Waters, it produces therapeutic mud, which is rated as one of the best.

However, the rest here is mainly seasonal in summer there is an influx of tourists, and in winter there is a lull. And if this situation is even more or less acceptable now, then a huge number of hotel and entertainment complexes that are currently being built on the territory of the Caucasian Mineral Waters may be unclaimed.

The main problem in the positioning of a tourist destination is the biased attitude of tourists to it, many do not even think of the region as a place where you can go, for example, on New Year's holidays or winter holidays with children. It should also be taken into account that tourist companies are starting to offer tours to the Caucasus Mineral Waters region only closer to summer.

All this together creates the impression that the Caucasian Mineral Waters region seems to "freeze" for the cold season in anticipation of heat, an influx of tourists and, accordingly, money. Thus, it is currently necessary to develop a program to promote the Caucasus Mineral Waters region as a year-round resort, especially since all the prerequisites for this are available.

We also reviewed the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia and its tourist resources to develop a strategy to increase the rating of its destinations. Andalusia, located in the southern part of the Iberian Peninsula, is an autonomous community of Spain and embodies the true flavor of this country, its proud spirit, multifaceted culture. Meanwhile, this region is interesting in itself – for its history, magnificent ancient

monuments, unique natural landscape and centuries-old traditions.

Among other regions of Spain, Andalusia ranks second in area, and there is more population here than in any other part of the kingdom. According to the 2016 census, 8,411,805 people live in Andalusia. Administratively, it is divided into eight provinces: Cordoba, Almeria, Cadiz, Granada, Jaen, Huelva, Seville and Malaga. The capital is the city of Seville.

The area of Andalusia is 87,268 km², which is 17.2% of the country's territory. It borders with other autonomous communities: in the north – with Extremadura and Castile-La Mancha, in the east – with Murcia. The Strait of Gibraltar and the Mediterranean Sea wash Andalusia from the south, and in the west there is a cordon with Portugal and there is access to the Atlantic Ocean.

The landscape of Andalusia is so diverse that it is able to impress even seasoned travelers. Here are the Sierra Nevada Mountains, the highest on the Iberian Peninsula. At sea level lie the coastal plains of the Guadalquivir River. The rainiest place in Spain, Sierra Alcornocales, is also here.

It is especially striking that in some 50 meters from the Mulacen peak, from which snow never leaves, there is a subtropical coast of Granada, and such contrasts are rarely found anywhere. Mountainous Andalusia is separated from the plain by the systems of the Bet Mountains and the Andalusian lowland. This is the only region on the map of Spain where the hot Mediterranean climate is adjacent to the cold of the mountain peaks.

Hot climatic conditions are observed in most of the autonomy. The summer period is characterized by high atmospheric pressure caused by anticyclones from the Azores. Severe drought is also characteristic of this time, interrupted from time to time by heavy downpours. With the onset of autumn, tropical anticyclones recede, the weather becomes unstable. Autumn, winter and spring are the time of torrential rains, although the air temperature does not decrease significantly. During the year there are about 75 rainy days in Andalusia, and in the driest areas – for example, on Cape Gata and the Tabernas Desert, the only one in Europe – only 50. From this we can make a simple conclusion that the sun shines here 300 days a year.

Due to the fact that Andalusia is a fairly extensive region, its guests do not lack a choice of tourist routes and entertainment. The history and culture of the Spanish, Arab and Moorish civilizations are closely intertwined on this land. Picturesque mountain areas suitable for hiking and hunting are combined with excellent beaches. Major cities abound with historical sites and cultural centers, not to mention entertainment

venues, large shopping malls and colorful, crowded markets. Tourists who find themselves in Andalusia are immersed in the festive atmosphere, which seems to permeate everything around.

The southernmost region of Spain is associated with tourists with the world-famous resorts of the coast, flamenco, bullfighting and Arab palaces preserved here since the time of the Caliphate. However, there are places in Andalusia where you can not only spend time comfortably, but also improve your health. We are talking about mineral springs. Balneotherapy in the region of Andalusia includes bathing in baths and pools, various showers, washing and rinsing, drinking and irrigation, they do inhalations and rinses.

In order to understand how advertising and PR technologies affect the tourist destinations of the Caucasian Mineral Waters and the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia, we investigated the opinion of potential tourists about the means of their promotion.

The research was conducted on the social network "Instagram" in 2022.

The empirical basis of the study was data on the tourist potential of the CMS region and the autonomous region of Andalusia, Spain.

The generality of the study: 100 respondents of the tourist destination of the Stavropol Territory.

The purpose of the study: to analyze and identify the most effective means of promoting the tourist destination of the Stavropol Territory.

Research method: questionnaire. The study used a standardized questionnaire consisting of 5 questions.

According to the analysis, we see that for the promotion of tourist destinations of the Stavropol Territory, such types of promotion as advertising and an Internet site are most often used (Figure 1).

Figure 1. What types of promotion of tourist destinations have you ever encountered?

Source: own elaboration.

According to the analyses, it is clear that the residents of Stavropol, as a type of promotion of a tourist destination, advertising is the most acceptable. Banners and souvenirs are in second place, Internet sites are in third place, and public relations are only in

fourth place, since this type of promotion is least known to respondents (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Which type of promotion of a tourist destination is most acceptable to you? Why?

Source: own elaboration.

The means of information about the tourist destination of Stavropol Territory, as shown by studies, are TV/Radio and the Internet, the easiest and simplest way of information, as well as from friends and relatives (Figure 3).

Figure 3. From what sources would you prefer to receive information about tourist destinations?

Source: own elaboration.

Studies show that, after all, residents of Stavropol prefer interesting and trustworthy advertising on the tourist market (Figure 4).

Figure 4. What, in your opinion, should be the advertising message about tourist destinations?

Source: own elaboration.

Respondents participating in the survey confirmed that the tourist region lacks newspaper

publications, instant lotteries and promotional souvenirs (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Name the disadvantages of the types of promotion of a tourist destination.

Source: own elaboration.

Respondents of the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia were asked the same questions.

The purpose of the study: to analyze and identify the most effective means of promoting the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia.

The generality of the study: 100 respondents of the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia.

According to the analysis, we see that to promote the autonomous region of Spain, Andalusia most often uses such types of promotion as advertising and an Internet site (Figure 6).

Figure 6. What types of promotion of the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia have you ever encountered?

Source: own elaboration.

According to the analysis, it is clear that the residents of the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia, as a type of promotion of a tourist destination, advertising is the most acceptable. Internet sites are in second place, banners and souvenirs are in third place, and public relations are only in fourth place, since this type of promotion is least known to respondents (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Which type of promotion of the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia is most acceptable to you? Why?

Source: own elaboration.

The media about the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia, as studies have shown, are TV/Radio and the Internet, the easiest and easiest way of information (Figure 8).

Figure 8. From which sources would you prefer to receive information about the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia?

Source: own elaboration.

Research shows that residents of the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia, as well as residents of the Stavropol Territory, prefer interesting, but confidential advertising on the tourist market (Figure 9).

Figure 9. What, in your opinion, should be an advertising message about the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia?

Source: own elaboration.

As a result of the study, respondents participating in the survey confirmed that the tourist region of the

autonomous region of Spain Andalusia also needs additional newspaper publications, instant lotteries and promotional souvenirs (Figure 10.).

Figure 10. Name the disadvantages of the types of promotion of the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia.

Source: own elaboration.

As a result of the conducted research, it was revealed that there is a need to raise the rating and more effective use of advertising and PR technologies to promote tourist destinations of the Caucasian Mineral Waters and the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia.

The following is the elaboration of a strategy to improve the ranking of tourist destinations in the two regions (mineral waters of the Caucasus and the Autonomous Community of Spain Andalusia) (Table 1).

The work, which at first will be quite difficult, nevertheless, will bring large profits in the future, allowing to maintain tourist flows, will increase the rating of the Caucasian Mineral Waters region and the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia.

Table 1. Elaboration of a strategy to improve the ranking of tourist destinations of the two regions (Caucasian mineral waters and the Autonomous Community of Spain Andalusia): basic concepts.

Authors	Concepts
I.S. Vazhenina, S.G. Vazhenin (2010)	Inefficient positioning in the world tourism market is considered by the expert community as "failures" of the state regulation of the industry and the reason for its low competitiveness. Such causal relationships should be taken into account in the context of promotion of the Stavropol destination, forming a holistic view on it as a unique tourist product, using a variety of unique advertising information tools developed and realized on the basis of the regional tourist information center, which should provide travel agents with a full range of information and marketing services.
A.P. Gorbunov, A.P. Kolyadin, L.Kh. Gazgireeva, L.A. Burnyasheva (2021)	Only an integrated approach will have a positive outcome.
M.A. Morozov, N.S. Morozov (2012)	It is important to pay attention to all the little things and follow developments to respond to the changing situation in time and act accordingly.
W.W. Smith, X.R. Li, B. Pan, M. Witte, S.T. Doherty (2015)	Everything is important: and what materials the media will present, and how the resort staff will work, meet the tourists, and how the special events will be organized, and whether the guests will come to them on the Press tour.

Source: own elaboration.

3 METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of the research is represented by a set of concepts that have developed in the Russian and foreign practice of researching the image of regions as tourist destinations.

In order to research the image of the regions – the Caucasian Mineral Waters and the Autonomous Region of Spain Andalusia as tourist destinations, historical and comparative methods were used to compare their features in different regions of the world.

The application of the process method was associated with the study of the formation of tourist destinations as a process and the identification of factors that have the most significant impact on its organization and further improvement.

The research was carried out in structural, functional, managerial aspects; it was based on the principles of consistency, complexity, determinism.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As a result of a comparative analysis, it turned out that the Caucasian Mineral Waters and the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia have similar features. Both regions are tourist destinations, similar in climatic features and natural resources, which attract both domestic and foreign travelers. But the main similarity is that these territories have a very strong balneological potential, which can serve as a promising incentive for the development of health tourism.

However, it was revealed that both Caucasian Mineral Waters and Andalusia are not actively engaged in their promotion, even despite the fact that health

tourism is developing in the region of Caucasian Mineral Waters, as well as Andalusia.

The proof of this is the data of the 7 ontente analysis of popular tourist sites of these regions (Figure 11, 12).

Figure 11. Popular types of tourism in the Caucasian Mineral Waters.

Source: own elaboration.

Figure 12. Popular types of tourism in Andalusia.

Source: own elaboration.

That is why we have developed a strategy to increase the rating of tourist destinations in the two regions based on the introduction of advertising and PR technologies. The strategy was developed for the Caucasus Mineral Waters region, with the aim of its application and promotion also by the autonomous region of Andalusia.

Changing opinions about a region is not an easy thing to do, because a stereotype that has been formed over the years cannot be broken in one day and make people think in a new way. It requires a comprehensive approach (table 2).

Table 2. A comprehensive approach to changing perceptions of the region.

Name of the approach	Specification
Creation of publications in the largest general and specialized media	Publications should contain information about the development of regions, new entertainment complexes, improved living conditions, unique natural resources, mountain slopes. The most successful option would be to create a story about the regions with an emphasis on winter holidays in various programs.
Posting articles on the Internet, on forums, in blogs, on the largest tourist sites	Information on forums and blogs should be presented in the most relaxed form, on behalf of the "happy tourist". Briefing with employees of hotel complexes about the living conditions, as well as providing them with all the necessary information on winter leisure in the vicinity of the complex location. It is also necessary to post information about the conditions of living in hotel complexes for the whole year.
Conducting briefing with employees of hotel complexes	Briefing with hotel employees about the living conditions, giving them all the necessary information on winter leisure. Posting information about the conditions of accommodation in hotels.
Creating special events that can attract tourists to the region	Organization of festivals and other various events. For the cold season, the organization of such events as: - autumn carnival or spring dances, - opening of the ski season, - New Year's events, - celebrations of anniversaries of cities, - holding winter sports championships, - holding celebrations of snow castles and reconstructions of past events, - holding days of a country with the organization of presentations on national topics and the invitation of representatives of that country.
Organization of press tours, both for employees of travel agencies and for potential tourists. In either case, it may be promotions.	For employees of travel agencies - as a reward to the best employee of the month, for tourists - for participating in any drawing. Special events, press tours help to attract tourists effectively. Sometimes press tours are held for journalists, in order to get a good article from them with positive reviews about the place of rest. In this case, a good organization of the trip is extremely important, as well as the coordination of the time of the tour with the holding of any events.
Organization of exhibitions and seminars of international scale	Participation in various exhibitions, for example, in Moscow MITT exhibitions "Travel and Tourism" and MITF fairs of St. Petersburg "INWETEX-CIS Travel Market and "Resorts", Sochi "Resorts and Tourism" and "Sports. Extreme. Active Recreation", in Spain - "Fitur" - an international tourism exhibition, which is held annually at the Ifema trade exhibition center in Madrid, has become one of

	the largest tourist fairs around the world, as well as on the Iberian Peninsula, "Intur" – an international tourism exhibition.
Creating a bank of photos and videos.	Creating a photo and video bank "Tourist Caucasian Mineral Waters" or "Photos of Andalusia" is a good selection of photos with sights, interesting places, parks, houses, residents, national food, landscapes, nature and cities of the region necessary for advertising campaigns and creating an image favorable for tourism.
Creating competitive digital films.	Creation of competitive digital films of artistic content covering new tourist routes in the Caucasus Mineral Waters region and the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia.
Publication of presentation books, booklets, brochures, posters, calendars, tourist maps, postcards and other printed products reflecting the tourist opportunities of the regions.	It is necessary to prepare publications in Russian, Spanish, English, German, French, Italian and Chinese for release.
Preparation of a series of brochures on different types of tourism.	Preparation of a series of brochures on different types of tourism, designed for different target audiences with a detailed description of the regional tourism product.
Placement of mock-up advertising in the tourist press.	Placement of mock-up advertising in the tourist press (professional and popular) about the regions and their tourist products, which are characterized by the absence of strict restrictions on the conditions of registration, have arbitrary sizes and presentation forms and involve the use of non-standard visual means.
The use of advertising magazines-catalogs, advertising directories.	The use of advertising magazines-catalogs, advertising directories to place accurate and detailed information about the conditions for the provision of tourist services in the Caucasian Mineral Waters and the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia.
Outdoor advertising placement with image blocks.	Placement of outdoor advertising with image blocks that would characterize the possibilities of recreation in specific resorts of the region (alternately about a separate city of tourist regions). Stationary outdoor advertising can be represented by posters, posters, strippers, billboards (billboards), billboards, signage. Transit outdoor advertising can be placed on vehicles (inside and outside).
Placement of network and point advertising of resorts and tourism.	Placement of network and point advertising of resorts and tourism of the Caucasian Mineral Waters and the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia on the radio in the format of radio ads, radio videos, radio magazines, radio reports, providing high selectivity and high speed of information, having a short period of advertising preparation and low costs for the creation and distribution of advertising.
Placement of television advertising about the tourist opportunities of the regions.	The placement of television advertising about the tourist opportunities of the Caucasian Mineral Waters regions and the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia, characterized by a wide audience, low financial costs for the distribution of advertising per viewer and having a strong impact on viewers. According to the form of execution, it can be a marking advertisement (in the form of a logo in the corner of the screen, or a 3-5-second screensaver); TV ads; demonstration clips; short films. It is advisable to use national television through distribution channels. According to J.M. Marcia (2021) implementation strategy involves the use of sponsored advertising, spot advertising, as well as advertising implemented on the basis of equity participation.
Creation of the heading "Pro CMS" or "Pro Andalusia" on tourist sites and geoportals of regions and countries as a tool for visualizing the results of research and promotion of destinations.	As a strategy for improving the rating of regions, we offer a rubric dedicated to regions. It is assumed that this heading will consist of several sections: – A historical essay about the Caucasian Mineral Waters region as a well-known balneological resort or the Andalusia region. – Getting to know the resort cities of the Caucasian Mineral Waters and the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia: – Balneological calendar. In our opinion, the most attractive events will be: – Interregional forum-exhibition "Treatment on CMS"; International tourist Exhibition "Leisure Recreation", the second most important specialized exhibition on the Russian market. – Sports and wellness program "Reach the source", for older guests; health and wellness tours and SPA in Andalusia according to their preferences. – Wellness quest game for children "City of health".

Source: own elaboration.

We have analyzed the features of PR technology and advertising events that affect the creation and promotion of the image of tourist destinations in the Stavropol Territory and the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia.

As a result of a comparative analysis, it turned out that the Stavropol Territory and the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia are very similar. Both regions are tourist destinations, similar in climatic features and

natural resources, which attract both domestic and foreign travelers. But the main similarity is that these territories have a very strong balneological potential, which can serve as a promising incentive for the development of health tourism. However, the sad fact is that neither the Stavropol Territory nor the autonomous region of Andalusia are interested in their promotion.

The study showed that only an integrated approach will have a positive result. It is important to pay attention to all the little things and monitor the development of events in order to react to the changing situation in time and act accordingly. Everything is important: what materials will be presented by the media, and how the staff of hotel complexes will work, meeting tourists, and how special events will be organized, and whether those invited to them will get on the press tour.

Summarizing, we can draw the following conclusions. In our information age, the development of tourism in specific regions and countries largely depends on the quantity and quality of information on the World Wide Web. In general, it must be remembered that only an integrated approach will have a positive result. It is important to pay attention to all the little things and monitor the development of events in order to react to the changing situation and act accordingly. Everything is important: what materials will be presented by the media, and how the staff of hotel complexes will work, meeting tourists, and how special events will be organized, and whether those invited to them will get on the press tour.

The work, which at first will be quite difficult, nevertheless, will bring large profits in the future, allowing to maintain tourist flows, will increase the rating of the CMS region and the autonomous region of Spain Andalusia.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The conducted research revealed that the region of the Caucasian Mineral Waters and Andalusia are not traditional tourist regions, but with the current tourist trends they are of great interest, especially their natural conditions and mountainous terrain, a lot of historical and architectural monuments, a peculiar culture and cuisine. Due to the sufficient number of tourist sites, their relatively uniform dispersal, the presence of a dense road network and cities near all tourist sites, the Caucasian Mineral Waters and Andalusia can be considered destinations.

Progressive modern information and communication technologies provide new opportunities: with the help of means and methods of advertising and PR technologies, they exert a regulatory influence on the state of economic, political, and cultural development of society.

The information activity of subjects in the tourism industry leads to an increase in the communicative impact in order to form the preferences of the target audience, broadcast cultural knowledge, norms, traditions and values, transform old into new stereotypes and behavioral practices.

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Table 1. CRediT author statement

Term	Definition	Autor 1	Autor 2	Autor 3
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	+	+	+
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	+		
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components			+
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	+		
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data		+	
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection			+
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	+	+	
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	+		
Writing – Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)		+	
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre- or post-publication stages			+
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation			+
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team		+	
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	+		
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication			+

Source: adapted from Elsevier (2022, s/p), based upon Brand et al. (2015).

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